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Trade Policy And Foreign Capital Inflows In West African Countries

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the effect of trade policy on foreign capital inflows in West Africa, using balanced panel data from 1993 to 2024. Foreign direct investment (FDI) was the dependent variable, while trade policy was captured through Import Penetration (IMP), Export Penetration (EXP), Degree of Trade Openness (DOP), Exchange Rate Policy (EXR), and Terms of Trade (TRT). Government Effectiveness (GOE) and Corruption Perception Index (COPI) served as control variables. The analysis focused on fifteen West African countries, reflecting the region's ongoing struggle to attract sustainable foreign capital despite multiple liberalization reforms. An ex post facto research design was employed, with data sourced from the World Development Indicators and Transparency International. The methodology combined descriptive statistics, correlation tests, cross-sectional dependence checks, panel unit root and cointegration tests, and regression estimations. Model selection was guided by Hausman and Redundant Fixed Effects tests, with the fixed effects specification ultimately adopted to test the hypotheses. The results showed that IMP, DOP, and EXR significantly and positively influence FDI inflows, highlighting the importance of openness to imports, liberalized trade, and exchange rate stability in fostering investment. In contrast, TRT had a significant negative effect on FDI, suggesting that favorable trade conditions, often linked to resource exports, may discourage diversified investment flows. EXP, GOE, and COPI were not statistically significant, indicating that export penetration and governance measures alone do not drive foreign capital in the region. The study concludes that effective trade policies, particularly those promoting openness and monetary stability, are central to attracting FDI in West Africa. However, policymakers must address structural rigidities and ensure macroeconomic gains translate into broad-based investment. Recommendations include boosting industrial capacity, refining export incentives, stabilizing exchange rates, and strengthening governance frameworks.

Keywords: Trade Policy, Import Penetration, Export Penetration, Degree of Trade Openness, Exchange Rate Policy, Terms of Trade, Government Effectiveness, Corruption Perception Index and Foreign Direct Investment.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, many nations have acknowledged that achieving sustainable growth requires strong trade integration, leading to evolving policies on tariffs, trade agreements, and regulatory frameworks that govern cross-border interactions (Afolabi et al., 2017). Key measures such as trade openness, import and

export penetration, and exchange rate policies play decisive roles in shaping foreign investment. Studies show that while high export volumes, stable exchange rates, and liberal trade practices encourage integration, they also require careful balancing to optimize capital inflows (Ogunsanwo et al., 2021). Efficient trade strategies, therefore, offer emerging economies like Nigeria opportunities to overcome challenges of infrastructure, regulation, and competitiveness (Mohsen, 2019).

For African economies reliant on exports, particularly oil, liberal trade frameworks are essential for reducing costs, improving market access, and creating a favorable climate for investors (Kalu, 2024). Countries that embrace openness often attract greater levels of foreign direct investment (FDI), highlighting the complementary link between trade and capital inflows (Erhijakpor et al., 2024). FDI in turn supports growth through gross capital formation, technology transfer, and productivity gains that enhance export capacity (UNCTAD, 2022). It also introduces managerial expertise and access to new markets, thereby strengthening balance of payments and stimulating local adaptation in production (Ehigiamusoe & Lean, 2019).

In West Africa, abundant natural resources and a large consumer market make the region highly attractive to investors. Liberalized trade policies that reduce barriers, alongside transparent regulations, encourage FDI while improvements in transport and energy infrastructure facilitate trade efficiency (Dumani et al., 2018). Political stability further strengthens investor confidence, whereas instability discourages inflows. Ultimately, FDI not only provides capital but also equips domestic firms with technology and expertise, enhancing their competitiveness in global markets. This interplay underscores how dynamic trade policies directly shape sustainable growth trajectories across Nigeria and the broader West African economy (Sayed & Vishwanatha, 2021).

Although the relationship between trade openness and foreign capital inflows has been widely examined, it remains unclear why investors are attracted to emerging economies that are often slow in adopting reforms and constrained by weak institutions. Some studies report positive outcomes, while others find negative or insignificant connections between openness and growth (Rahman, 2016). Gilal et al. (2016) also emphasized this inconsistency, noting that while some scholars argue openness drives growth, others claim countries may benefit more without it. Kalu (2024) revealed that exchange rate volatility had a negative but insignificant effect on FDI in Nigeria, highlighting the vulnerability of capital inflows to currency instability. In contrast, Kumari et al. (2023) found no long-term relationship between FDI, trade openness, and growth in India, suggesting outcomes are highly context-specific. Akorsu and Okyere (2023) reported that trade openness hindered industrial development in Ghana, showing that liberalization can negatively impact sectoral growth. Alfalih (2024) demonstrated that key macroeconomic variables could worsen unemployment in Saudi Arabia, yet their interaction with trade policy remains insufficiently explored. Yu and Wang (2023) further identified geopolitical risks and trade dependence as important factors shaping FDI flows. Similarly, Liu and Wang (2023) observed that FDI in services affects manufacturing dynamics, while Wang et al. (2023) linked investment to industrial structures. Mawutor et al. (2023) highlighted the importance of self-selection in Indonesia's trade participation but overlooked policy influence. Consequently, this study investigates how specific trade policies, including import penetration, export penetration, openness, exchange rate, and terms of trade, affect foreign capital inflows into West Africa.

Conceptual Review

Trade Policies

Trade policies encompass rules and measures governing cross-border exchange of goods, services, and capital, including tariffs, quotas, subsidies, and agreements (Sayed & Vishwanatha, 2021). They regulate imports and exports while aligning trade with national goals (Afolabi et al., 2017). Beyond facilitating commerce, they protect domestic industries, stimulate employment, promote diversification, and enhance competitiveness (Agu et al., 2016). Trade policies also narrow disparities between advanced and developing economies through market access, technology transfer, and cooperation (Bakari, 2017). In today's globalized economy, they extend to environmental sustainability, digital trade, supply chain

disruptions, and geopolitical risks (Chang et al., 2020). Regional and multilateral frameworks such as AfCFTA harmonize rules, deepen cooperation, and support inclusive growth (Leal-Arcas et al., 2024). In West Africa, trade outcomes reflect colonial and monetary legacies dividing Anglophone and Francophone states. Francophone economies like Senegal and Côte d'Ivoire, operating under the CFA franc, benefit from currency stability but face reduced policy autonomy (Kohnert, 2022). By contrast, Anglophone countries such as Nigeria and Ghana enjoy flexible regimes but endure exchange rate volatility (Comparative Colonial Systems, 2023). Non-tariff barriers and weak trade finance persist across both blocs, though institutional responses differ (IFC & WTO, 2022). ECOWAS and AfCFTA promote convergence, yet legal, regulatory, and monetary divergences remain (World Bank, 2022). Francophone states maintain stability but limited diversification, while Anglophone counterparts pursue reforms amid institutional weaknesses (UNCTAD, 2023). Harmonized trade laws, unified border systems, and hybrid frameworks balancing stability with flexibility are essential for deeper West African integration (OECD, 2020).

Import Penetration Policy (IMP): IMP measures imports relative to exports, designed in Nigeria to balance trade, generate revenue, control inflation, and drive diversification (Manyok, 2016). While it protects local industries (Agu, 2015), it can raise food prices (Idisi, 2021), restrict private trade (Ferreira et al., 2021), and reduce regional welfare (Anania & Bee, 2018). Yet it enhances customs revenue, curbs smuggling, and shifts trade flows toward Nigeria (Gereffi et al., 2021; Wagna, 2022).

Export Penetration Policy (EXP): EXP promotes stable export growth through trade agreements, infrastructure, and market strategies (Jiyong et al., 2020). By shifting from consumer to capital goods, it fosters industrialization and technology (Su & Yao, 2017). For Nigeria, diversifying beyond oil is vital for competitiveness (Kotishwar, 2020). High-value exports generate foreign exchange, attract FDI, and spur sustainable growth (Sunde, 2017; Etim & Daramola, 2020).

Degree of Trade Openness (DOP): DOP, the ratio of imports and exports to GDP, enhances growth via technology access, markets, and capital inflows (Ramzan et al., 2019). However, openness also exposes economies to global shocks and imbalances (Barrot et al., 2018).

Terms of Trade (TOT): TOT reflects export-to-import price ratios. Improvements strengthen stability, while deteriorations reduce competitiveness and FDI attraction (Sachs & Warner, 1995).

Exchange Rate Policy (EXR): Nigeria's history of fixed and flexible regimes highlights persistent volatility and depreciation (Kalu et al., 2019; Nwokoro, 2017). Exchange rate shifts affect inflation, lending, and investment, requiring hedging strategies (Osho & Efuntade, 2019).

Foreign Capital Inflows

Foreign capital inflows (FCI) are vital external resources that support growth, modernization, and global integration. They originate from individuals, firms, or governments, bringing funds, expertise, technology, and market access (Egbuwalo & Abere, 2018). FCIs may take the form of cash, assets, intellectual property, or investments in infrastructure, stocks, and real estate (Siejel, 2021). Major channels include foreign direct investment (FDI), portfolio investment, loans, remittances, and grants, with their volume shaped by governance, stability, and global conditions (Nurasheva et al., 2024). While inflows finance infrastructure, health, and education, they also influence exchange rates, inflation, and interest rates, creating both opportunities and risks (Alshubiri, 2022). Overreliance can trigger capital flight and instability, making sound policies and absorptive capacity essential (Makrelov et al., 2022).

FDI is the most significant FCI, involving lasting ownership or managerial control in a foreign enterprise (IMF, 2020). It occurs as greenfield projects or mergers and acquisitions, measured as inflows or stock (World Bank, 2018). Nigeria, Sub-Saharan Africa's largest FDI recipient, has experienced fluctuations, with inflows falling from USD 3.5 billion in 2017 to 1.9 billion in 2018. FDI types include export-oriented (notably oil), market-driven, and government-led projects such as Ajaokuta Steel and the LNG plant at Bonny (Fofana et al., 2018; Aderemi et al., 2020). While FDI can enhance productivity and growth, mixed outcomes highlight the need for strategic alignment to maximize impact.

Theoretical Review

This study is anchored on Patrick's (1966) Intervention Theory and the Dependency Theory to explain the dynamics of foreign capital inflows. Intervention Theory draws from classical and dependency perspectives, arguing that government action is needed to keep economies open to foreign capital, which can stimulate growth, jobs, and technology transfer. It emphasizes balancing regulation and openness so that foreign direct investment (FDI) and other inflows align with national development priorities. Seid (2002) notes that excessive intervention deters investors, while excessive liberalization risks misalignment with socio-economic goals. Thus, governments must design policies that attract and safeguard foreign inflows while ensuring an investor-friendly environment.

By contrast, Dependency Theory cautions against overreliance on external capital. It contends that while foreign investment may spur short-term growth, it often entrenches dependence, external control, and inequality. Inflows can exploit local resources, limit policy autonomy, and deepen structural vulnerabilities. For West Africa, where resource exports and external finance dominate, such warnings are particularly relevant.

Thus, these theories provide a balanced framework. Intervention Theory supports openness and foreign capital attraction, while Dependency Theory highlights risks of external domination. Policymakers must therefore strike a middle ground—leveraging foreign capital for transformation without undermining sovereignty or creating structural dependency.

Empirical Review

Fidrmuc, Gaibulloev, Mirzaei, and Moore (2024) analyzed capital inflows and capital goods imports in credit-constrained industries across 57 developing countries (2000–2020). Using panel regression on 11 sectors, they found capital inflows eased financial constraints, enabling higher imports of capital goods and boosting productivity. Kastratović (2024) studied FDI inflows and agricultural exports in 80 developing countries (2005–2017) with system-GMM and cointegration tests. Results confirmed FDI enhanced agricultural exports in both short and long terms by raising production and competitiveness. Menson, Birat, and Magaji (2024) examined aid inflows and investment volatility in 19 Sub-Saharan African states (1980–2018) using CS-DL and bootstrap causality. Aid reduced volatility overall, but sudden aid cuts sharply increased instability, underscoring dependency risks. Yeboah and Lamin (2024) assessed trade openness, FDI, and debt in Ghana (1991–2022) using ARDL and Granger causality. They found FDI and debt boosted growth, while openness hindered it. Causality revealed sensitivity of growth to external dynamics. Okeke and Ezeala (2024) explored trade effects on Nigeria's manufacturing (1999–2022) with OLS. Imports reduced manufacturing GDP, exports improved it, and balance of payments weakened growth, showing import reliance constrains industrial expansion. Akinola and Ohonba (2024) investigated FDI, debt servicing, and growth in Nigeria (2011–2022) using ARDL and Granger tests. Results showed FDI, debt, and exchange rates positively influenced growth, though declining FDI and rising debt were concerns. They recommended prudent debt management. Akorsu and Okyere (2023) examined FDI and trade openness in Ghana (1983–2019) using ARDL and NARDL. Findings showed FDI consistently promoted industrialization, while negative trade openness shocks reduced it. Rao, Sethi, Dash, and Bhujabal (2023) studied foreign aid and Ethiopia's growth (1974–2017) using ARDL and ECM. Aid negatively affected growth in both the short and long run, with adjustment to equilibrium at 84.6% per year, suggesting aid dependence harms sustainability. Gök and Güvercin (2020) analyzed FDI, FPI, and growth in 25 Sub-Saharan African states (1990–2016) using panel VAR. Both flows complemented each other, promoting growth despite volatility and systemic weaknesses. Together, these studies highlight how capital inflows; FDI, aid, debt, and trade affects real sector growth, with outcomes shaped by governance, sector focus, and dependency risks.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study adopted an ex post facto research design, suitable for analyzing existing datasets and relationships among variables. The population comprised sixteen West African countries, but due to data

gaps, fifteen were sampled. Data spanning 1993–2024 were obtained from the World Development Indicators and Transparency International. Independent variables included import penetration, export penetration, degree of trade openness, exchange rate policy, and terms of trade, while dependent variables were foreign capital inflows (FDI, portfolio investment, debt inflows, and remittances). Control variables were the political stability index and corruption perception index. Analysis employed panel regression techniques in E-Views 9.0. Descriptive statistics summarized the data, and correlation analysis checked associations and multicollinearity. Cross-sectional dependence was tested using Breusch Pagan LM, Pesaran CD, and Friedman tests. Stationarity was examined through Levin Lin Chu, Im-Pesaran-Shin, and Fisher ADF panel unit root tests. For I(1) series, Johansen Fisher Panel Cointegration tested long-run relationships. Model specification was guided by redundant fixed effects and Hausman tests, with fixed effects controlling heterogeneity and random effects applied where assumptions held. Coefficients were significant at $p < 0.05$. Positive signs indicated direct relationships, negative signs inverse ones. The framework builds on prior studies (Sayed & Vishwanatha, 2021; Morina et al., 2020; Ramzan et al., 2019) but uniquely integrates all trade policy and capital inflow variables for West Africa. Hence, our model is stated below:

$$FDI_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 IMP_{it} + \beta_2 EXP_{it} + \beta_3 DOP_{it} + \beta_4 EXR_{it} + \beta_5 TRT_{it} + \beta_6 GOE_{it} + \beta_7 COPI_{it} + U_t$$

Where:

FDI= Foreign Direct Investments

IMP = Import Penetration Policy

EXP = Export Penetration Policy

DOP = Degree of Trade Openness

EXR = Exchange Rate Policy

TRT = Terms of Trade

GOE = Government Effectiveness

COPI = Corruption Perception Index

α_i =Entity-specific fixed effects (if fixed-effects GMM is used).

β_0 = Constant Value

β_1 - β_7 = Parameter Estimate

U_t = Error Term (It is assumed to be heteroskedastic and possibly auto-correlated across both entities and time periods)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The empirical foundation of the study focused on examining how trade policy dynamics influenced foreign capital inflows in West African economies. Balanced panel data covering the period 1993 to 2024 was employed, integrating dimensions of trade policy such as IMP, EXP, DOP, EXR, and TRT, together with institutional controls including GOE and the COPI. FDI served as the dependent variable, capturing the flow of foreign capital into the region. The analytical tests were selected to assess the statistical properties, interrelationships, and structural dynamics of the variables, ensuring alignment with the study's scope. Beyond methodological rigor, these tests provided a comprehensive lens for evaluating both the short-run and long-run impacts of trade policy on FDI.

Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics provided an overview of the variables across West Africa, highlighting trends in FDI, trade policy indices, and institutional quality over 31 years. By presenting means, deviations, and ranges, the analysis identified patterns, outliers, and skewness, guiding transformations and robustness checks. Results are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

	FDI	IMP	EXP	DOP	EXR	TRT	GOE	COPI
Mean	7.346833	12.63450	12.58730	59.66394	77.29614	99.75281	-0.009250	53.89540
Median	7.145000	12.75000	12.78600	60.54500	75.55850	10.04200	-0.060000	54.58000
Maximum	15.00000	19.96900	19.99100	99.87000	49.12840	9.128300	2.500000	99.80000
Minimum	0.170000	5.074000	5.078000	20.13000	5.020000	7.000000	-2.500000	10.00000
Std. Dev.	4.283156	4.466328	4.315437	22.75492	42.62969	16.98519	1.451159	25.67159
Skewness	0.096577	-0.055714	-0.048149	-0.048331	0.031084	-0.041926	0.030982	0.017061
Kurtosis	1.800866	1.731143	1.824328	1.826939	1.819991	1.802024	1.762851	1.853826
Jarque-Bera Probability	2.950463 0.077128	3.244830 0.066781	7.282954 0.078131	7.270830 0.061811	7.292570 0.000001	8.284354 0.048211	3.068756 0.000000	6.229758 0.078122
Sum	3526.480	60645.59	60419.03	28638.69	371021.5	47881.35	-4.440000	25869.79
Sum Sq. Dev.	8787.458	955513.2	892041.4	248019.6	87048212	138189.9	1008.709	315675.6
Observations	480	480	480	480	480	480	480	480

Source: E-Views 9.0 Output, (2025).

Table 1 summarizes descriptive statistics for 480 observations, highlighting variability and distributional features of the study’s variables. FDI averaged 7.35 with moderate dispersion and approximate normality. IMP and EXP showed balanced central tendencies and near-normal flat distributions. DOP averaged 59.66 with wide dispersion but remained broadly symmetric. EXR displayed high volatility and strong non-normality, while TRT showed mild deviation from normality. GOE varied widely with strong evidence of non-normality, whereas COPI was near normal despite large variability. Overall, most variables were symmetric and flat, though some exhibited deviations, warranting robust econometric techniques.

Correlation Analysis

Correlation analysis measured the strength and direction of relationships among study variables, highlighting potential multicollinearity and preliminary associations between FDI and trade policy measures. Correlations near ±1 indicate strong links, while values above 0.7 between independent variables suggest multicollinearity. Results are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Correlation Analysis

	FDI	IMP	EXP	DOP	EXR	TRT	GOE	COPI
FDI	1.000000							
IMP	-0.007266	1.000000						
EXP	-0.044363	-0.019703	1.000000					
DOP	0.013437	-0.072983	0.088002	1.000000				
EXR	0.050640	0.052220	-0.064703	0.038284	1.000000			
TRT	-0.049703	0.060714	-0.001520	-0.051361	-0.030036	1.000000		
GOE	-0.017168	-0.005121	0.038475	-0.039276	0.118378	0.052828	1.000000	
COPI	0.002198	0.014954	-0.082750	-0.032428	0.010927	-0.072763	0.004134	1.000000

Source: E-Views 9.0 Output, (2025).

Table 2 reports correlation coefficients among the study variables, highlighting weak or negligible linear associations between FDI and trade policy indicators. FDI showed near-zero correlations with IMP, EXP, DOP, EXR, TRT, GOE, and COPI, suggesting limited direct relationships. Similarly, trade-related variables and institutional indicators exhibited weak or inconsistent associations, with no values approaching strong correlation thresholds. The absence of significant linear links indicates that the dynamics between FDI, trade policy, and institutional quality are complex, likely involving non-linear effects, indirect channels, or lagged influences. These findings justify the application of advanced econometric methods for deeper structural analysis.

Residual Cross-Sectional Dependence Tests

Given the multi-country dataset, cross-sectional dependence was tested to capture possible regional shocks or policy spillovers in West Africa. Correlated residuals across countries may bias estimates if ignored. A p-value below 0.05 rejects independence, confirming the need for second-generation panel estimators. Results appear in Table 3.

Table 3: Residual Cross-Section Dependence Test

Null hypothesis: No cross-section dependence (correlation) in residuals

Equation: Untitled

Periods included: 32

Cross-sections included: 15

Total panel observations: 480

Note: non-zero cross-section means detected in data

Cross-section means were removed during computation of correlations

Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Breusch-Pagan LM	97.74283	105	0.6796
Pesaran scaled LM	-1.535891		0.1246
Pesaran CD	1.151120		0.2497

Source: E-Views 9.0 Output, (2025).

Table 3 reports the residual cross-section dependence test, assessing whether residuals across West African countries were correlated. Using 480 panel observations, mean adjustments were made to avoid systematic bias. The Breusch-Pagan LM statistic (97.74, p = 0.6796), Pesaran scaled LM (-1.54, p = 0.1246), and Pesaran CD (1.15, p = 0.2497) all produced probabilities above 0.05. These results consistently failed to reject the null hypothesis, confirming no significant cross-sectional dependence. Thus, residuals were independently distributed across countries, validating a key assumption of panel data estimators and supporting the reliability of subsequent econometric analyses.

Panel Unit Root Test

Unit root tests were applied to verify the stationarity of variables and prevent spurious regressions. Stationarity ensures suitability for regression and cointegration analysis. A p-value below 0.05 indicates stationarity; otherwise, differencing or cointegration methods are required. Results are presented in Table 4 below.

Table 4: Panel Unit Root Test

Variables	Method	Statistics	Prob.	@ Level	Check Stationary for
FDI	Levin, Lin & Chu t	-10.2426	0.0000	1(0)	Stationary
	Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	-11.6849	0.0000	1(0)	
	ADF - Fisher Chi-square	184.612	0.0000	1(0)	
	PP - Fisher Chi-square	293.934	0.0000	1(0)	
IMP	Levin, Lin & Chu t	-7.16234	0.0000	1(0)	Stationary
	Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	-10.0421	0.0000	1(0)	
	ADF - Fisher Chi-square	-10.2382	0.0000	1(0)	
	PP - Fisher Chi-square	321.408	0.0000	1(0)	
EXP	Levin, Lin & Chu t	-9.66957	0.0000	1(0)	Stationary
	Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	-10.7898	0.0000	1(0)	
	ADF - Fisher Chi-square	170.762	0.0000	1(0)	
	PP - Fisher Chi-square	334.875	0.0000	1(0)	
DOP	Levin, Lin & Chu t	-9.37499	0.0000	1(0)	Stationary
	Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	-9.70710	0.0000	1(0)	
	ADF - Fisher Chi-square	149.965	0.0000	1(0)	
	PP - Fisher Chi-square	287.685	0.0000	1(0)	
EXR	Levin, Lin & Chu t	-7.09530	0.0000	1(0)	Stationary
	Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	-9.58575	0.0000	1(0)	
	ADF - Fisher Chi-square	147.764	0.0000	1(0)	
	PP - Fisher Chi-square	286.077	0.0000	1(0)	

	Levin, Lin & Chu t	-9.71660	0.0000	1(0)	Stationary
	Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	-11.8704	0.0000	1(0)	
	ADF - Fisher Chi-square	188.583	0.0000	1(0)	
TRT	PP - Fisher Chi-square	311.225	0.0000	1(0)	
	Levin, Lin & Chu t	-6.12941	0.0000	1(0)	Stationary
	Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	-9.48648	0.0000	1(0)	
	ADF - Fisher Chi-square	145.568	0.0000	1(0)	
GOE	PP - Fisher Chi-square	280.129	0.0000	1(0)	
	Levin, Lin & Chu t	-9.75013	0.0000	1(0)	Stationary
	Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	-11.2951	0.0000	1(0)	
	ADF - Fisher Chi-square	179.516	0.0000	1(0)	
COPI	PP - Fisher Chi-square	325.846	0.0000	1(0)	
Variables	Method	Statistics	Prob.	@1st Diff.	Check for Stationary
	Levin, Lin & Chu t	-15.6119	0.0000	1(1)	Stationary
	Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	-20.8620	0.0000	1(1)	
	ADF - Fisher Chi-square	341.080	0.0000	1(1)	
FDI	PP - Fisher Chi-square	379.531	0.0000	1(1)	
	Levin, Lin & Chu t	-12.6983	0.0000	1(1)	Stationary
	Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	-21.2647	0.0000	1(1)	
	ADF - Fisher Chi-square	351.354	0.0000	1(1)	
IMP	PP - Fisher Chi-square	343.052	0.0000	1(1)	
	Levin, Lin & Chu t	-14.2951	0.0000	1(1)	Stationary
	Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	-19.1700	0.0000	1(1)	
	ADF - Fisher Chi-square	317.806	0.0000	1(1)	
EXP	PP - Fisher Chi-square	363.857	0.0000	1(1)	
	Levin, Lin & Chu t	-16.3025	0.0000	1(1)	Stationary
	Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	-20.0242	0.0000	1(1)	
	ADF - Fisher Chi-square	332.231	0.0000	1(1)	
DOP	PP - Fisher Chi-square	335.411	0.0000	1(1)	
	Levin, Lin & Chu t	-15.9346	0.0000	1(1)	Stationary
	Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	-22.4159	0.0000	1(1)	
	ADF - Fisher Chi-square	366.418	0.0000	1(1)	
EXR	PP - Fisher Chi-square	370.734	0.0000	1(1)	
	Levin, Lin & Chu t	-16.3322	0.0000	1(1)	Stationary
	Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	-20.6059	0.0000	1(1)	
	ADF - Fisher Chi-square	342.510	0.0000	1(1)	
TRT	PP - Fisher Chi-square	359.833	0.0000	1(1)	
	Levin, Lin & Chu t	-11.5682	0.0000	1(1)	Stationary
	Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	-18.4347	0.0000	1(1)	
	ADF - Fisher Chi-square	304.838	0.0000	1(1)	
GOE	PP - Fisher Chi-square	399.203	0.0000	1(1)	
	Levin, Lin & Chu t	-14.8346	0.0000	1(1)	Stationary
	Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	-20.5785	0.0000	1(1)	
	ADF - Fisher Chi-square	343.063	0.0000	1(1)	
COPI	PP - Fisher Chi-square	351.465	0.0000	1(1)	

Source: E-Views 9.0 Output, (2025).

Table 4 reports the panel unit root test results, assessing the stationarity of variables using Levin, Lin & Chu, Im-Pesaran-Shin, ADF-Fisher, and PP-Fisher methods. At level, all variables (FDI, IMP, EXP, DOP, EXR, TRT, GOE, COPI) were stationary, with test statistics significant at $p = 0.0000$. At first difference, results remained consistent, confirming integration of order one. For instance, IMP showed -21.2647 (IPS) and 343.052 (PP-Fisher), both highly significant. The consistent rejection of non-stationarity across methods indicates the data is stable, reliable, and suitable for cointegration and long-run equilibrium analysis.

Johansen Fisher Panel Cointegration Test

The Johansen Fisher Panel Cointegration Test evaluated whether FDI and trade policy indicators shared a long-run equilibrium despite short-term fluctuations. Cointegration was confirmed if at least four of seven

statistics were significant at $p < 0.05$, validating stable long-run relationships and justifying further econometric analysis. Results appear in Table 5.

Table 5: Johansen Fisher Panel Cointegration Test

Series: FDI IMP EXP DOP EXR TRT GOE COPI

Date: 07/17/25 Time: 17:00

Sample: 1993 2024

Included observations: 480

Trend assumption: Linear deterministic trend

Lags interval (in first differences): 1 1

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Trace and Maximum Eigenvalue)

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Fisher Stat.* (from trace test)	Prob.	Fisher Stat.* (from max-eigen test)	Prob.
None	689.9	0.0000	334.7	0.0000
At most 1	354.2	0.0000	181.4	0.0000
At most 2	200.1	0.0000	78.70	0.0000
At most 3	131.0	0.0000	53.06	0.0058
At most 4	89.75	0.0000	55.38	0.0032
At most 5	71.36	0.0000	28.53	0.5426
At most 6	70.19	0.0000	38.25	0.1433
At most 7	96.47	0.0000	96.47	0.0000

Source: E-Views 9.0 Output, (2025).

Table 5 presents the Johansen Fisher panel cointegration results for FDI, IMP, EXP, DOP, EXR, TRT, GOE, and COPI from 1993 to 2024. Using both trace and maximum eigenvalue tests, results show strong rejection of no cointegration, with highly significant statistics at lower ranks ($p = 0.0000$). Even up to the fourth rank, probabilities remain below 0.05, confirming multiple long-run associations. Higher ranks show weaker significance, but sufficient evidence exists to establish robust cointegration. Overall, findings confirm a stable long-term equilibrium among the variables, supporting the adoption of long-run econometric models in subsequent analysis.

Redundant Fixed Effects Tests VS Correlated Hausman Test

The test assessed whether country-specific effects improved model fit over pooled regression, addressing unobserved heterogeneity. A p-value below 0.05 justified fixed effects. The Hausman test then distinguished between fixed and random effects, rejecting the null if regressors correlated with country-level errors. Results are shown in Table 6 below.

Table 6: Redundant Fixed Effects Tests VS Correlated Hausman Test

Redundant Fixed Effects Tests

Equation: Untitled

Test cross-section fixed effects

Effects Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section F	1.962749	(14,458)	0.0191
Cross-section Chi-square	27.967585	14	0.0144

Correlated Random Effects - Hausman Test

Equation: Untitled

Test cross-section random effects

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	6.764984	7	0.4538

Source: E-Views 9.0 Output, (2025).

Table 6 reports the redundant fixed effects and Hausman tests to determine the best panel model. The fixed effects test produced significant results ($F = 1.9627$, $p = 0.0191$; Chi-square = 27.97, $p = 0.0144$), rejecting the null and confirming cross-country heterogeneity. The Hausman test (Chi-square = 6.7650, $p = 0.4538$) showed random effects are consistent. While both models appear viable, fixed effects are preferred due to their robustness in capturing unobserved heterogeneity across 15 countries, ensuring more reliable estimation of the relationship between trade policies, institutional factors, and foreign capital inflows.

Fixed Effect Pooled Regression

The regression model controlled for country-specific factors, isolating the effects of trade policies on FDI across West Africa. Coefficient signs and p-values guided interpretation, with significance confirmed at $p < 0.05$. This allowed identification of meaningful policy impacts on FDI. Results are presented in Table 7 below.

Table 7: Fixed Effect Pooled Regression

Dependent Variable: FDI
 Method: Panel Least Squares
 Date: 07/17/25 Time: 16:25
 Sample: 1993 2024
 Periods included: 32
 Cross-sections included: 15
 Total panel (balanced) observations: 480

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	8.666545	1.665974	5.202089	0.0000
IMP	0.026102	0.004415	5.912118	0.0000
EXP	-0.004473	0.004611	-0.969962	0.3326
DOP	0.021872	0.008721	2.507969	0.0302
EXR	0.000954	0.000468	2.038462	0.0427
TRT	-0.031733	0.011668	-2.719661	0.0251
GOE	-0.056368	0.137084	-0.411193	0.6811
COPI	-0.004023	0.007709	-0.521814	0.6021

Effects Specification

Cross-section fixed (dummy variables)

R-squared	0.863358	Mean dependent var	7.346833
Adjusted R-squared	0.820412	S.D. dependent var	4.283156
S.E. of regression	4.239217	Akaike info criterion	5.771384
Sum squared resid	8230.700	Schwarz criterion	5.962683
Log likelihood	-1363.132	Hannan-Quinn criter.	5.846579
F-statistic	14.75284	Durbin-Watson stat	2.015115
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000686		

Source: E-Views 9.0 Output, (2025).

Table 7 reports the fixed effects pooled regression results with FDI as the dependent variable and IMP, EXP, DOP, EXR, TRT, GOE, and COPI as predictors. Using 480 balanced panel observations, the model explains 86% of FDI variation ($R^2 = 0.8634$, adjusted $R^2 = 0.8204$). The constant term is positive and significant, indicating a stable baseline. The F-statistic (14.7528, $p = 0.0007$) confirms overall significance, while the Durbin-Watson statistic (2.0151) suggests no serious autocorrelation. These findings validate the robustness of the fixed effects model in explaining the relationship between trade policy variables and FDI across West African countries.

The findings revealed a positive and significant effect of IMP on FDI, suggesting that higher levels of imports attract more foreign capital inflows. This aligns with Patrick's (1966) Intervention Theory, which advocates for policies that create openness to foreign capital as a means of stimulating growth and industrial capacity. By increasing imports, especially of capital goods, countries create demand that foreign investors may wish to meet. Fidrmuc *et al.* (2024) similarly found that capital inflows eased constraints in credit-dependent industries, facilitating the import of capital goods that enhanced productivity. However, Dependency Theory would caution that excessive reliance on foreign imports could weaken domestic production, mirroring Okeke and Ezeala's (2024) result where imports negatively affected Nigeria's manufacturing GDP. Thus, while IMP attracts FDI, policy must balance openness with strategies to build local competitiveness.

EXP showed no significant effect on FDI, implying that greater export volumes alone do not directly attract foreign capital. This partially contrasts with Intervention Theory, which posits that openness and trade expansion support capital inflows. Instead, the result may reflect Dependency Theory's warning that focusing on exports of raw commodities offers little developmental gain. Kastratović (2024) found FDI boosted agricultural exports, but in Nigeria's context, over-dependence on primary commodities may dilute FDI's growth-enhancing potential. Similarly, Yeboah and Lamin (2024) noted trade openness in Ghana hindered growth in the long run, indicating that without diversification and structural transformation, exports may not be sufficient to encourage stable FDI inflows.

DOP positively and significantly influenced FDI, affirming that liberal policies encourage investment. This supports Intervention Theory's stance on openness as a driver of growth, investment, and technological transfer. The result is consistent with Akinola and Ohonba (2024), who showed FDI and external openness positively impacted Nigeria's GDP, and Gök and Güvercin (2020), who found liberalized capital flows fostered growth in Sub-Saharan Africa. However, Dependency Theory would highlight the risks of excessive liberalization, as Akorsu and Okyere (2023) found negative shocks in trade openness reduced Ghana's industrialization. Thus, while openness attracts FDI, governments must moderate policies to ensure inflows strengthen, rather than undermine, domestic industries.

EXR policy showed a significant positive effect on FDI, implying that stable or favorable currency dynamics support investor confidence. This resonates with Intervention Theory, which underscores the role of government in maintaining conditions conducive for foreign capital. Akinola and Ohonba (2024) also confirmed exchange rates positively influenced Nigeria's GDP alongside FDI. However, Dependency Theory warns that reliance on external capital tied to currency stability can expose economies to global shocks. Menson *et al.* (2024) showed sudden changes in external flows increased volatility in Sub-Saharan Africa, underscoring the risks of exchange rate fluctuations. Policymakers must therefore manage exchange rate policies carefully to attract FDI while mitigating volatility.

The negative and significant relationship between TRT and FDI suggests that improvements in trade conditions may paradoxically reduce capital inflows. This finding echoes Dependency Theory, which emphasizes structural vulnerabilities, as reliance on favorable trade conditions can discourage diversified investment. Rao *et al.* (2023) similarly found foreign aid harmed Ethiopia's growth, highlighting that external conditions may create long-term dependence rather than self-sustaining development. Conversely, Intervention Theory would argue for policies that attract FDI regardless of shifts in trade conditions. The result implies that West African economies may experience reduced inflows when improved terms of trade lessen the perceived urgency for foreign investment.

GOE showed no significant impact on FDI, indicating that institutional quality did not directly shape inflows in the sample. This result partly contradicts Intervention Theory, which emphasizes the role of effective governance in creating investor-friendly climates. Instead, it aligns more closely with Dependency Theory's caution that structural weaknesses limit the developmental benefits of capital inflows. Yeboah and Lamin (2024) found Ghana's growth was sensitive to external debt and FDI but less influenced by institutional quality in the short term. This suggests that foreign investors may prioritize market opportunities and trade conditions over governance quality, particularly in resource-rich contexts.

Similarly, COPI had no significant effect on FDI, suggesting that perceived corruption did not deter foreign capital in the studied context. From a Dependency Theory lens, this supports the argument that external investors may prioritize access to resources or markets over institutional transparency, often perpetuating exploitative dynamics. Intervention Theory would argue that governance reforms should still be pursued to sustain long-term investment confidence. Empirical evidence from Gök and Güvercin (2020) shows that both FDI and FPI contributed positively to growth despite volatility and weak institutions, reinforcing the notion that investors sometimes overlook governance issues if profitability prospects remain attractive.

CONCLUSION

This study concludes that trade policy instruments significantly shape foreign direct investment (FDI) inflows into West Africa, though with varying effects. Import penetration (IMP) shows a strong positive impact, signaling viable markets that attract investors. Trade openness (DOP) also encourages FDI by reducing barriers and enhancing market efficiency. Exchange rate stability (EXR) exerts a modest but significant effect, emphasizing the role of predictable monetary conditions. Conversely, terms of trade (TRT) negatively influence FDI, likely reflecting structural dependence on resource exports that deter diversification. Government effectiveness (GOE) and corruption perception (COPI) are insignificant, suggesting investors often prioritize returns over institutional quality. Overall, liberal import policies, openness, and exchange rate stability should anchor investment strategies, while governance reforms must be integrated into broader policy frameworks. Attracting sustainable FDI requires aligning trade policies with diversification and inclusive development goals.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the study put forward the following recommendations:

- i. Strengthen domestic capacity to accommodate imports and encourage industrial linkages that can absorb foreign investment and promote local value addition.
- ii. Pair export promotion policies with infrastructure development and targeted production incentives to enhance their attractiveness to foreign investors.
- iii. Sustain and deepen trade liberalization efforts, particularly by advancing regional integration and harmonizing tariffs to create a more unified and investor-friendly market.
- iv. Maintain exchange rate stability through coordinated monetary and fiscal policy to provide the predictability and financial assurance that foreign investors seek.
- v. Monitor the structural effects behind improvements in terms of trade to avoid unintended consequences such as sectoral imbalances or crowding out of FDI in non-traditional industries.
- vi. Invest in practical governance reforms that go beyond perception indices, focusing on regulatory efficiency, enforcement of contracts, dispute resolution, and ensuring long-term policy stability to build investor confidence.

REFERENCES

- Adeiza, A. (2021). Business Environment, Trade, Competitiveness and Product Space Mapping (BETCPSM).
- Agu, C. (2015). Resource inflow, import leakages and growth linkages: Why remittance flows are not optimised in Nigeria. *CENTRAL BANK OF NIGERIA*, 53(3), 74.
- Akinola, G. W., & Ohonba, A. (2024). The effects of external debt and foreign direct investment on economic growth in Nigeria. *Economies*, 12(6), 142.
- Akorsu, P. K., & Okyere, S. (2023). Trade openness, foreign direct investment and industrialisation in Ghana. *Cogent Economics & Finance*, 11(1), 2183638.
- Alshubiri, F. (2022). The impact of the real interest rate, the exchange rate and political stability on foreign direct investment inflows: A comparative analysis of G7 and GCC Countries. *Asia-Pacific Financial Markets*, 29(3), 569–603.

- Anania, P., & Bee, F. K. (2018). Emerging global trends and the opportunities for African co-operatives in improving members' wellbeing. *Journal of Co-operative and Business Studies (JCBS)*, 1(1), 1–22.
- Barrot, L. D., Calderón, C., & Servén, L. (2018). Openness, specialization, and the external vulnerability of developing countries. *Journal of Development Economics*, 134, 310–328.
- Chang, Y., Iakovou, E., & Shi, W. (2020). Blockchain in global supply chains and cross border trade: A critical synthesis of the state-of-the-art, challenges and opportunities. *International Journal of Production Research*, 58(7), 2082–2099.
- Cheng-Chwee, K. (2017). Explaining the contradiction in China's South China Sea policy: Structural drivers and domestic imperatives. *China: An International Journal*, 15(1), 163–186.
- Comparative colonial systems and economic resilience in West Africa. (2023). *Journal of African Studies*, 41(1), 65–82.
- Etim, E., & Daramola, O. (2020). The informal sector and economic growth of South Africa and Nigeria: A comparative systematic review. *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity*, 6(4), 134.
- Ferreira, J. P., Ramos, P., Barata, E., Court, C., & Cruz, L. (2021). The impact of COVID-19 on global value chains: Disruption in nonessential goods production. *Regional Science Policy & Practice*, 13, 32–54.
- Fidrmuc, J., Gaibullov, K., Mirzaei, A., & Moore, T. (2024). The effect of capital inflows on the imports of capital goods in developing countries. *Journal of Corporate Finance*, 84, 102531.
- Gereffi, G., Lim, H. C., & Lee, J. (2021). Trade policies, firm strategies, and adaptive reconfigurations of global value chains. *Journal of International Business Policy*, 4(4), 506.
- Gök, A., & Güvercin, D. (2020). The interaction between foreign direct investment, foreign portfolio investment and economic growth: The case of Sub-Saharan African countries. *Akademik İncelemeler Dergisi*, 15(1), 57–82.
- Idisi, P. O. (2021). Food security, economic growth and price stability nexus and conceptual issues. *Economic and Financial Review*, 59(4), 9–31.
- IFC & WTO. (2022). *Trade finance in West Africa: Gaps, challenges, and opportunities*. World Bank Group and World Trade Organization.
- Kastratović, R. (2024). The impact of foreign direct investment on agricultural exports: The evidence from developing countries. *The Journal of International Trade & Economic Development*, 33(2), 276–293.
- Kohnert, D. (2022). The CFA franc and France's economic footprint in Africa: Monetary imperialism revisited. *Review of African Political Economy*, 49(172), 189–207.
- Leal-Arcas, R., Alsheikh, A., Maqtoush, J., Althunayan, N., Dal Berto, H., Alsayed, L., ... & Afaneh, B. (2024). Trade, geopolitics, and environment. *Journal of Infrastructure, Policy and Development*, 8(7), 5114.
- Makrelov, K., Davies, R., & Harris, L. (2022). The impact of capital flow reversal shocks in South Africa: A stock-and-flow-consistent analysis. In *Capitalism: An Unsustainable Future?* (pp. 145–171). Routledge.
- Mawutor, J. K. M., Sogah, E., Christian, F. G., Aboagye, D., Preko, A., Mensah, B. D., & Boateng, O. N. (2023). Foreign direct investment, remittances, real exchange rate, imports, and economic growth in Ghana: An ARDL approach. *Cogent Economics & Finance*, 11(1), 2185343.
- Nurasheva, K. K., Shalabayev, I. I., Abdikerimova, G. I., Kulanova, D. A., & Mergenbayeva, A. T. (2024). Capital inflow and investment attractiveness of Central Asian countries (on the example of Kazakhstan). *Regional Science Policy & Practice*, 100039.
- OECD. (2020). *West African cross-border policy networks*. OECD West Africa Series.
- Okeke, I. C., & Ezeala, G. (2024). Foreign trade and manufacturing industry in Nigeria: An empirical review (1999–2022). *African Banking and Finance Review Journal*, 12(12), 185–194.

- Pan, W., Xie, T., Wang, Z., & Ma, L. (2022). Digital economy: An innovation driver for total factor productivity. *Journal of Business Research*, 139, 303–311.
- Rodríguez-Pose, A., & Hardy, D. (2015). Addressing poverty and inequality in the rural economy from a global perspective. *Applied Geography*, 61, 11–23.
- Sachs, J., & Warner, A. (1995). Economic reform and the process of global integration. *Brookings Papers on Economic Activity*, 1, 1–118.
- Siegel, J. J. (2021). *Stocks for the long run: The definitive guide to financial market returns & long-term investment strategies*. McGraw-Hill Education.
- Su, D., & Yao, Y. (2017). Manufacturing as the key engine of economic growth for middle-income economies. *Journal of the Asia Pacific Economy*, 22(1), 47–70.
- Sunde, T. (2017). Foreign direct investment, exports and economic growth: ADRL and causality analysis for South Africa. *Research in International Business and Finance*, 41, 434–444.
- UNCTAD. (2023). *Trade and development report: Building productive capacities in West Africa*. United Nations Conference on Trade and Development.
- World Bank. (2022). *Africa regional integration and trade facilitation update*. <https://www.worldbank.org>
- Yeboah, E., & Lamin, C. (2024). The dynamic effect of trade openness, debt, and foreign investment in Ghana's economy: An ARDL bound testing approach. *International Journal of Engineering and Management Sciences*, 1–19.